

Tracking a Thawing World: The Global Terrestrial's Network for Permafrost new Data Platform is now online

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Permafrost covers nearly one quarter of the Northern Hemisphere's land surface, storing vast amounts of carbon. As the climate warms, permafrost temperatures are rising globally, destabilizing landscapes and infrastructure and releasing greenhouse gases such as methane and carbon dioxide. Long-term observations are essential to understand permafrost responses to warming and to estimate its future role in global carbon emissions. The Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) is the main international program for sustained permafrost monitoring. Researchers from over 30 countries collect permafrost temperature (PT) and active layer thickness (ALT) data, shared through the GTN-P platform. The original system, launched in 2015, has become outdated, prompting the development of a modernized database. Developed at the Alfred Wegener Institute's Permafrost Research Section under the GTN-P Steering Committee and within the Arctic PASSION Horizon2020 project, the new GTN-P data platform is going to be the central platform for sharing and accessing permafrost data. It supports the Permafrost ECV products PT and ALT and will soon include Rock Glacier Velocity.

The new GTN-P platform features an intuitive interface, flexible data downloads, and time-series visualization tools. An annual global data compilation includes co-authorship for contributors, and additional synthesized products will be provided. Collaboration with the WMO ensures adherence to international data standards, enhancing interoperability and compliance with FAIR Data Principles. For data providers, the streamlined upload process includes automated quality checks with real-time feedback. Supported by AWI's IT infrastructure, the new GTN-P platform strengthens accessibility, reliability, and sustainability for the global permafrost research community.